

Needs Analysis of Developing Interactive E-Assessment Based on Educational Games to Improve Students' Motivation and Science Learning Outcomes in Junior High School

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to develop an interactive e-assessment based on educational games using the Zep Quiz application to improve students' motivation and learning outcomes in science subjects. The background of this study is based on the low level of students' motivation and learning outcomes, especially on the topic of elements, compounds, and mixtures. The assessments used so far have been conventional, making them less attractive and unable to actively engage students in the learning evaluation process. Therefore, a preliminary study consisting of literature review and field study is needed. The assessment developed is an interactive e-assessment based on educational games for daily science assessments. This study aims to analyze interactive e-assessment to improve motivation and learning outcomes of eighth-grade students. This research used a qualitative descriptive approach. Data collection instruments included interview questionnaires for teacher needs analysis and student needs analysis questionnaires. The results showed that teachers stated students were very enthusiastic and enjoyed participating in daily assessments presented in the form of educational games. The interview results with students showed that 60% of students enjoyed participating in daily science assessments, while 90% stated that they would be more motivated if the assessments were presented in the form of games. A total of 77% of students expected teachers to use educational games in daily assessments, and more than 90% believed that educational games could make science learning more enjoyable and increase learning enthusiasm. Furthermore, 77% of students felt that educational games could help them understand the material more quickly, and 93% reported feeling more confident when answering questions in game-based formats. In addition, 80% of students stated that they could remember science lessons more easily when using educational games compared to only reading textbooks. As many as 87% of students also acknowledged that their learning motivation increased when educational games were used. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the development of interactive e-assessment based on educational games is important to improve motivation and science learning outcomes of eighth-grade junior high school students.

KEYWORDS: E-Assessment, Educational Games, Learning Motivation, Learning Outcomes, Science Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Science learning assessment plays a very important role in measuring the level of success at the end of the learning process. (Budiono & Hatip, 2023) stated that assessment results function to identify students' needs in the learning process in order to achieve the expected learning outcomes. However, assessments that are still conducted manually tend to make students less active and less motivated. This condition is one of the factors causing students' learning outcomes to be lower and the learning process to become less effective.

The development of digital technology has had a significant impact on the field of education, particularly in the learning and assessment processes. The use of technology enables learning to become more effective, interactive, and accessible anytime. (Fadil Julianto & Sidhiq Andriyanto, 2025) stated that one approach proven to improve students' motivation and learning outcomes is gamification, which refers to the application of game elements in learning contexts. Currently, technology plays an important role as a primary means of improving the quality of education. Therefore, the integration of technology in education has become an essential necessity. The use of learning multimedia is considered an effective medium for delivering knowledge

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because it can present materials visually by integrating text, audio, graphics, and animation into a unified display that engages both visual and auditory senses (Game et al., 2013).

Currently, teachers are required to be able to utilize technology in developing engaging learning media and assessments. One of the innovations in education is the development of interactive e-assessments based on educational games. One solution to overcome the problems mentioned above is the use of multimedia that can increase students' interest in learning, such as educational games (Dan et al., 2018). The use of technology provides opportunities for teachers to present more engaging learning assessments, including assessments through educational games, which can also motivate students to study more actively. (Erawati, 2023) stated that the assessment of students' learning outcomes does not always have to be conducted in the form of traditional examinations; students can complete assignments through electronic questions using game-based learning applications.

Based on observations conducted at SMP Negeri 1 Lubuk Sikaping, it was found that most students had not yet achieved learning mastery. The data showed that more than 70% of students did not meet the Learning Objectives Achievement Criteria (KKTP). This condition indicates problems in the learning process and the assessment methods being used. In addition, manual assessment methods cause delays in providing feedback to students. According to Nasution et al. (2020), learning integrated with technology can improve students' creativity and help teachers design more engaging learning experiences. One of the most common uses of technology by teachers is in the assessment process.

Monotonous conventional assessments tend to make students lose interest and feel pressured. Therefore, more interactive and enjoyable assessment innovations are needed so that students can learn more effectively. According to Melianti Dotutinggi and Alwiyanto Zees (2023), educational games make learning more interesting, encourage students to be more active in the learning process, and help them understand the material more easily.

One solution that can be implemented is the use of interactive e-assessment based on educational games, such as Zep Quiz. (Wiwin Handoko, Eva Mizkat, Auliana Nasution, & Hambali, 2021) stated that gamification-based assessments are able to increase learning motivation and provide rapid feedback. Therefore, the development of interactive e-assessments based on educational games is expected to significantly improve students' motivation and learning outcomes.

II. METHODS

This study employed a qualitative approach, in which the researcher did not initially determine how previous events were related to the variables being investigated. One of the main characteristics of qualitative research lies in its focus on intensive studies of specific situations, such as cases and phenomena (Muhammad et al., 2024).

This study was conducted at SMP Negeri 1 Lubuk Sikaping, involving 315 eighth-grade students and two science teachers as research subjects. The data collection instruments used included teacher needs analysis interview sheets, student needs analysis questionnaires, and students' test score results.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The needs analysis was conducted to identify gaps between the existing learning conditions in integrated science learning, particularly in the development of assessments that can improve students' motivation and learning outcomes. The collected data were then analyzed descriptively to describe the actual needs in the field, both from teachers' and students' perspectives, as a basis for designing relevant and interactive educational game-based e-assessments.

Results of Curriculum Needs Analysis

Table 1. Needs Analysis of Curriculum in the Document Aspect

No	Component	Question	Analysis
1	Learning Outcomes (CP)	Do the learning outcomes for the topic of elements, compounds, and mixtures refer to the appropriate phase and educational level?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
2	Learning Objectives Flow (ATP)	Has the learning objectives flow for this topic been systematically designed and supported scientific competencies?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
3	Learning Objectives	Do the learning objectives include conceptual understanding, observation skills, and scientific communication skills?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available

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4	Teaching Module	Is there a specific teaching module for the topic of elements, compounds, and mixtures that is contextual and interactive?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
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Based on the results of the curriculum needs analysis on the topic of elements, compounds, and mixtures, it was found that the learning components are available and aligned with the implementation of instruction. The Learning Outcomes (CP) have referred to the appropriate phases and educational levels, while the Learning Objectives Flow (ATP) has been systematically designed to support the development of students' scientific competencies. In addition, the learning objectives include conceptual understanding, observation skills, and scientific communication abilities. Teaching modules for the topic of elements, compounds, and mixtures are also available using contextual and interactive approaches. These findings indicate that the curriculum tools currently used have adequately supported the science learning process.

Table II. Needs Analysis of Curriculum Based on the Learning Material Content Aspect

No	Component	Question	Analysis
1	Contextualization	Is the material related to everyday phenomena, such as methods of separating mixtures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
2	Content Relevance (Actuality)	Are there updates or enrichment of materials based on recent developments in astronomy?	<input type="checkbox"/> Available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Available
3	Concept Visualization	Is the material supported by visual media or simulations to facilitate students' understanding?	<input type="checkbox"/> Available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Available
4	Science Literacy Enhancement	Are students encouraged to explore scientific facts from reliable sources and interpret data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Available

Based on the results of the analysis of learning material content, it was found that the material has been connected to everyday life phenomena, such as methods of separating mixtures, which can help students understand concepts in a more contextual manner. However, the material has not been supported by updated information reflecting recent developments, visual media or simulations to enhance learning, and activities that promote scientific literacy through the exploration of scientific facts and data interpretation. These findings indicate that although the material is already related to real-life situations, further development is needed to make learning more interactive, up-to-date, and supportive of students' scientific literacy skills.

Table III. Needs Analysis of Curriculum Based on the Learning Process Aspect

No	Component	Question	Analysis
1	Learning Strategy	Are experimental methods, observations, and group discussions used in the learning process?	<input type="checkbox"/> Available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Available
2	Use of Learning Media	Does the teacher use learning media to visualize methods of separating mixtures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
3	Student Engagement	Are students given opportunities to explore concepts through small projects or observations?	<input type="checkbox"/> Available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Available
4	Science Integration	Does the learning process integrate science with technology, geography, and local culture?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
5	Learning Environment	Is the classroom managed to support active and collaborative discussions?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available

Based on the results of the analysis of the learning process, it was found that the implementation of instructional methods such as experiments, observations, and group discussions has not been carried out optimally. Students have also been given limited opportunities to explore concepts through small projects or observation activities. However, teachers have utilized learning media to help visualize the topic of mixture separation. In addition, the learning process has integrated science concepts with technology, geography, and local culture, while the classroom environment has supported active and collaborative

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discussions. These findings indicate that the learning process already includes several supporting aspects, but improvements are still needed in instructional strategies and students' active involvement.

Table IV. Needs Analysis of Curriculum Based on the Learning Evaluation Aspect

No	Component	Question	Analysis
1	Formative Assessment	Does the teacher conduct digital assessments to measure students' understanding?	<input type="checkbox"/> Available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Available
2	Projects or Products	Are students given opportunities to practice mixture separation techniques?	<input type="checkbox"/> Available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Available
3	Summative Assessment	Does the final evaluation reflect conceptual understanding and scientific thinking skills?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
4	Learning Reflection	Do students reflect on the learning process and outcomes?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available
5	Teacher Feedback	Does the teacher provide constructive feedback and encourage further exploration?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Available <input type="checkbox"/> Not Available

Based on the results of the analysis of learning evaluation, it was found that digital assessments to measure students' understanding, as well as practical activities related to mixture separation techniques, have not yet been implemented in the learning process. However, the final evaluation has reflected students' conceptual understanding and scientific thinking skills. In addition, learning reflection activities have been conducted, and teachers have provided constructive feedback to support students' learning processes. These findings indicate that the evaluation aspect of learning has been implemented fairly well, although further development is still needed in the use of digital assessments and practical activities to create more active and meaningful learning experiences.

Results of Teacher Needs Analysis

The analysis of teachers' needs regarding learning resources and instructional media was conducted through interviews using the following interview guidelines:

1. What curriculum is currently implemented at your school according to your subject area?
2. What assessment systems have been applied at SMP Negeri 1 Lubuk Sikaping for daily assessments? Are they conducted manually or digitally through electronic systems?
3. In your opinion, what are the strengths and weaknesses of the daily assessment system that has been implemented so far?
4. Have you ever used educational game-based assessments for daily evaluations?
5. In your opinion, would students enjoy daily assessments if they were conducted through educational games?
6. Have you ever heard of or used digital/electronic educational game-based evaluations in daily assessments during the learning process?
7. What is your opinion about evaluation methods using educational games?
8. According to your perspective, to what extent can educational games help improve students' learning motivation?
9. Have you ever measured the level of students' learning motivation?
10. How do you determine the level of students' learning motivation?
11. In your opinion, how would you describe the level of students' learning motivation?
- 12.

The teachers' needs for interactive e-assessment based on educational games are presented in the following table:

Table VI. Results of Teachers' Needs Analysis During Observation

No.	Analysis Results
1	The curriculum implemented at the school for all grade levels is the Merdeka Curriculum.
2	The assessment system used at SMP Negeri 1 Lubuk Sikaping for daily assessments is still conventional.
3	The weaknesses of the daily assessment system previously implemented at the school include limited accuracy, time constraints, the risk of causing student stress, and students' lack of interest in reading and understanding questions.

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4	Digital daily assessments have been implemented by several teachers using platforms such as Quizizz and Kahoot.
5	According to the teachers' assessment, students would enjoy daily assessments if they were conducted through educational games.
6	Teachers have heard of and used digital educational game-based evaluations in daily assessments.
7	Teachers believe that evaluation through educational games is very effective because students become more motivated to study harder.
8	According to teachers' perceptions, educational games are very helpful in improving students' motivation and learning outcomes.
9	Teachers have measured students' learning motivation levels.
10	Teachers identify students' learning motivation levels by observing the learning process. Some students show low enthusiasm during lessons, do not ask questions, and are reluctant to complete assignments.
11	Students' current level of learning motivation is still relatively low. This can be seen from students who are reluctant to complete assignments, lack focus during lessons, and often arrive late to class.

Percentage

The students' needs for interactive e-assessment based on educational games are presented in the following table:

Table VII. Students' Needs Analysis Questionnaire Results

No	Questions	Total		Percentage	
		Yes	No	Yes	No
1	Do you enjoy participating in daily science assessments?	18	12	0%	40%
2	Do you feel that daily assessments often make you nervous in science subjects?	16	27	53%	90%
3	Would you like your science teacher to use educational games for daily assessments in class?	23	7	77%	23%
4	Do you think educational games can make science learning more enjoyable?	28	2	93%	7%
5	Do you feel more motivated to learn science if the assessments use educational games?	27	3	90%	10%
6	Do you think educational games can help you understand science material more quickly?	23	7	77%	23%
7	Do you feel more confident answering science questions if they are presented in a game format?	28	2	93%	8%
8	Do you find it easier to remember science lessons through educational games compared to only reading textbooks?	24	6	80%	20%
9	Do you think daily science assessments using educational games can improve your learning outcomes?	26	4	87%	13%

The analysis of students' needs for interactive e-assessment based on educational games is presented in the following table:

Table VIII. Results of Students' Needs Analysis

No.	Analysis of Responses
1	60% of students enjoyed participating in daily science assessments, while 40% reported that they did not enjoy them.
2	53% of students felt that daily science assessments made them feel tense, while 47% did not feel tense.
3	77% of students wanted science teachers to use educational games for daily assessments in class, while 23% did not.
4	93% of students believed that educational games could make science learning more enjoyable, while 7% disagreed.
5	90% of students felt more motivated to learn science if daily assessments used educational games, while 7% did not feel more motivated.

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6	77% of students believed that educational games could help them understand science material more quickly, while 23% disagreed.
7	93% of students felt more confident in answering science questions when presented in the form of educational games, while 8% disagreed.
8	80% of students found it easier to remember science lessons through educational games compared to reading, while 20% disagreed.
9	87% of students believed that science assessments using educational games could improve learning outcomes, while 13% disagreed.

Discussion

Curriculum Needs Analysis of Grade VIII Science Textbooks

Material analysis is conducted to identify relevant learning content, determine the level of difficulty, and adjust the presentation of the material to support effective digital learning. The analyzed materials generally refer to national curriculum documents (such as the Merdeka Curriculum or the 2013 Curriculum), syllabus, and lesson plans implemented in schools. This means that the curriculum used should be aligned with the conditions of the educational institution and the characteristics of students. The process of analyzing learning materials aims to ensure that the content complies with established regulations, is relevant to students' needs, and can be adapted to regional potential as well as the characteristics of the educational institution. Therefore, the implementation of web-based educational game e-assessment in evaluating learning activities is considered effective and relevant to current conditions in improving students' learning motivation both at school and at home. This gamification media provides an enjoyable learning experience, encouraging students to understand the material more deeply and actively participate during the learning process. Zep Quiz not only helps students remember the material but also fosters greater interest in learning (Ni et al., 2026).

Based on the results of the Grade VIII science curriculum analysis, the learning planning has referred to the Merdeka Curriculum. The Learning Outcomes (CP) are aligned with the established phases and educational levels, while the Learning Objective Flow (ATP) has been systematically designed to support students' scientific competencies. The learning objectives also cover aspects of conceptual understanding, observation skills, and scientific communication. In addition, teaching modules for this material are already available. In general, the curriculum is in accordance with the requirements of the Merdeka Curriculum; however, the implementation of learning and evaluation still requires improvement, particularly in terms of innovative learning media and digital assessment. The use of educational game-based learning media such as ZEP Quiz has been found to be effective in increasing learning motivation, providing immediate feedback, and helping to map students' understanding in greater detail (Agnes et al., 2025)

Analysis of Learning Environment Needs

The environmental analysis was conducted to identify the conditions of the school learning environment. The analyzed aspects included the availability of facilities, infrastructure, and network accessibility to support the implementation of educational game-based daily assessments. Learning motivation is influenced by several factors, including internal factors such as individual needs, interests, and values, as well as external factors such as the learning environment, teaching, and social support (Tasmara et al., 2025).

The results of the environmental analysis indicate that the science learning outcomes of Grade VIII students are still relatively low, and students' learning motivation needs to be improved. Students tend to show low enthusiasm when participating in science tests or assessments, and this condition directly affects their learning achievement. The low level of learning motivation is caused by the lack of student response during the learning process and limited active involvement during evaluations. Assessment implementation has not fully engaged students actively. The school supports the development of technology-based assessments, and the Merdeka Curriculum also requires assessments that are more meaningful and competency-oriented. One solution to overcome these issues is the use of multimedia that can increase students' interest in learning through attractive user interface designs, one of which is educational games (Armansyah & Buchari Nurdin, 2025). The school's Wi-Fi network is relatively stable, and most students have devices such as smartphones. This indicates that, in terms of facilities, the school has significant potential to develop assessments based on educational games or interactive digital platforms.

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Analysis of Teacher Needs

The needs analysis was obtained from the results of teacher interview analysis. Teacher needs analysis is the initial stage that is highly important in the evaluation development process. This step aims to identify the problems faced by teachers in the evaluation process as well as their needs for media or learning resources that can optimally support students' understanding of the material. Digital education enables teachers to use various tools and resources, such as videos, simulations, and interactive content, to enhance students' learning experiences (Ashari et al., 2023).

Based on the interview results with teachers, the school has implemented the Merdeka Curriculum. The daily assessment system currently used is still conducted manually. Teachers also observed that students are often reluctant to read and understand questions in depth. The learning motivation of Grade VIII students in science subjects is considered to be at a moderate to low level. This is reflected in students' lack of active participation during the learning process, unstable learning interest, and the tendency to delay completing assignments. Several teachers have previously used interactive educational games such as Quizizz and Kahoot for daily assessments, and students showed high enthusiasm when assessments were conducted in the form of educational games. Educational game-based assessments are considered capable of improving motivation and learning outcomes because they create an enjoyable learning environment and encourage students to be more enthusiastic in answering questions. According to Agnes et al. (2025), the use of educational game-based learning media such as ZEP Quiz is effective in increasing learning motivation, providing immediate feedback, and helping to map students' understanding in detail.

Analysis of Student Needs

Student analysis aims to identify students' conditions and characteristics. The aspects analyzed include students' experiences with science daily assessments, particularly those related to the use of learning media by teachers. This analysis is expected to support the process of developing evaluation media that can be effectively utilized by teachers. Research conducted by (Santiaji et al., 2025) supports that the Zep Quiz platform provides solutions to two common issues encountered in educational settings, namely offering adaptive learning methods and increasing students' motivation, thereby reducing anxiety and learning fatigue while making the learning process more interactive and enjoyable.

The results of interviews with students showed that 60% of students enjoyed participating in daily science assessments, while 90% stated that they would be more enthusiastic if daily assessments were designed in the form of games. A total of 77% of students expected teachers to use educational games in daily assessments, and more than 90% stated that educational games make science learning more enjoyable and increase learning motivation. Furthermore, 77% of students felt that educational games could help them understand the material more quickly, and 93% reported feeling more confident when answering questions presented in game format. In addition, 80% of students stated that they found it easier to remember science lessons when using educational games compared to only reading textbooks. As many as 87% of students also acknowledged that their learning motivation increased when using the educational game ZEP Quiz. These findings are consistent with previous research, which showed that the implementation of ZEP Quiz was effective in creating an active and competitive learning environment, thereby encouraging students to participate actively in the learning process (Dhea Widyaningrum, Azhar Ahmad Smaragdina, Dion Dwi Rizky, & Yanuar Eko Ardiansyah, 2025).

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the needs analysis conducted, it can be concluded that the development of interactive e-assessment based on educational games is highly needed in Grade VIII junior high school science learning to improve students' motivation and learning outcomes. The analysis results indicate that the assessment system, which is still conventional in nature, causes students to become easily bored, feel anxious, and show low enthusiasm in participating in daily assessments. These conditions have an impact on students' learning outcomes, making them less than optimal, particularly in the topic of elements, compounds, and mixtures.

The results of interviews and questionnaires showed that most students were enthusiastic about the use of educational games in daily science assessments. Students felt happier, more motivated, more confident, and found it easier to understand and remember the material when assessments were conducted in the form of educational games. In addition, teachers also considered that the use of educational games could improve students' motivation and learning outcomes, while creating a more engaging and conducive classroom learning environment.

Based on the results of the curriculum, learning environment, teacher, and student needs analyses, the school has a strong opportunity to implement educational game-based e-assessment because it is supported by the Merdeka Curriculum, adequate technological facilities, and the availability of digital devices owned by students. Therefore, the development of

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interactive e-assessment based on educational games using the ZEP Quiz application is considered relevant and feasible to be developed as an innovation in science learning assessment. The use of this e-assessment is expected to help improve students' motivation and learning outcomes, as well as increase students' active participation during the learning process.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, several recommendations can be proposed. First, for teachers, it is recommended to integrate the use of e-assessment in a well-planned manner in order to continuously monitor students' understanding development. Second, for the school, it is suggested to support the implementation of interactive game-based e-assessment by providing adequate supporting facilities, such as a stable internet connection and training for teachers in the use of learning technologies. Third, for future researchers, it is recommended to further develop interactive game-based e-assessment products, implement them in different subject matter, and add features that enable communication between teachers and students.

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